

SMART ATTENDANCE SYSTEM

PROF ANIL PATIL
Guide

GIRIJA BELDAR
Group Members

BHAGYASHRI GADEKAR
Group Members

RAJANEE GUND
Group Members

SHITAL GUND
Group Members

PRIYANKA KHYADE
Group Members

ABSTRACT

Managing the attendance using traditional approach is really a cumbersome process. The person has to maintain the attendance record in registers and file using pen and paper.

-The problem with this approach is that it requires lots of paper which are the part of our non-renewable natural resources.

-We are in the age, where we have to think about sustainable development.

-Managing the attendance using mobile phones, provide an alternative way in this direction.

-The mobile application we have attempted to build will require connecting to the internet through WiFi (Wireless Fidelity) technology or through GPRS(General Packet Radio Service).

-Lecturers will first have to sign up for this and then they can take attendance any time they wish by first logging in with the help of a smart phone to the server.

-After attendance has been taken lecturer will send it over to sever via GPRS. The lecturers can also enroll new students, delete information about a particular student, modify some information etc.

INTRODUCTION

Attendance is a vital part of daily routine in educational institutes, offices and many other organizations.

-In schools and colleges this attendance marking is done manually but with advent of new technologies like smart phones, ipads, tablets, palmtops the world is just a click away.

-Today, we need not use pen and paper based attendance registers instead we can use very easy and efficient methods like taking e-attendance.

-Based on this idea we have made a project which is an Android based mobile application (MAttS App) here "M" stands for Mobile "Att" is abbreviation for Attendance and "S" stands for System.

-This mobile application will require connecting to the

internet through Wi-Fi(Wireless Fidelity) technology or through GPRS(General Packet Radio Service).

-Lecturers will first have to sign up for this and then they can take attendance any time they wish by first logging in with the help of a smartphone to the server.

-After attendance has been taken lecturer will send it over to sever via GPRS.-The lecturers can also enroll new students, delete information about a particular student, modify some information etc.

-With this project we aim at reducing the manual efforts taken daily by the lecturers the time being wasted and also we want to emphasize on reducing the paper wastage that happens daily.

DESCRIPTION

Better than PC based System

It is better than PC based system in many ways:

In an environment of inadequate and erratic Power (Electricity) supply, the Mobile phones are much better than the Computer; Desktop or Laptop.

The Mobile phone requires a small fraction of the power requirement of Computers and has power storing batteries that tend to store power for a longer period, when compared to Laptops. It provides mobility to the users to access the attendance record at any time and any place.

The Mobile Phone is relatively cheaper than the Computer on the average so economically it has advantage over that.

In an environment of poor maintenance culture, Mobile phones are less prone to malfunctioning when compared to Computers So, Cheaper Maintenance is the next added advantage for any system based on mobile phones.

The reduction in Paper material being used in traditional method of pen and paper based attendance system, thus preserving the Forests of the world (the small phone can contain hundreds of thousands of pages of books, and written materials). It is a Green technology. Availability wise also it is preferable, today mobile phone is available to every other person as compared to computer. So, any

institution does not need to incur any extra cost while installing the system.

IMPLEMENTATION:

The mobile attendance system has been built to eliminate the time and effort wasted in taking attendance in collage .It also greatly reduces the amount of paper resource needed in attendance data management. The system is divided into following modules. This is an android mobile application it's built to be used for collage faculty so that they may take student attendance on their phones.This application will be based on the different modules like:

List of Modules in this Mobile phone based Attendance System Project:

1.Student Attendance List Creation - Once this application is installed on a phone, it allow user to create a student attendance sheet consisting of name, roll no ,date, absent/present marks & subject. Teacher has to fill student names along with associated roll no.

2.User - Teacher need to enter user name and password to enter this page, then only they can take attendance from mobile phones.

3.Attendance entry - This module for marking the attendance of the students. They select branch, year and semester of the students. After that they mark to the absentees.

4. Attendance Storage - This data is now stored in file faculty mobile phone, faculty may also view it anytime on their mobile phone.

5. Attendance Sheet Transfer - The faculty can transfer the file to a server via an internet connection where this data can be stored and maintained by the school/collage

6. Attendance Check - The pc operator can check the Attendance transferred as students roll no,date, time and sort by date to check presentees & absentees of particular date.

7.GPS connectivity - With this function they send attendance list to the server that store the attendance in the database. It selects cell phone through GPS.

8.Update database - This module manipulate the attendance list when it receives the signal from the cell phone.

9.Display - This module is for students, they can check their attendance, they need to select their year, semester and branch.

REFERENCES

- 1) <https://www.ijarcse.com>
- 2) www.arpnjournals.com
- 3) www.google.com
- 4) www.yahoo.com